

Kinetics of Chromic Acid Oxidation of Serine, Methionine and Cysteine

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Oxidation of serine, methionine and cysteine was carried out in perchloric acid media by chromic acid. The reactions were found to be first order each in oxidant, reducing substrate and perchloric acid concentrations. Thus the rate of the reaction is given by the unified expression

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CrO}_3] = k[\text{Chromic acid}][\text{Substrate}][\text{H}^+]$$

Added salts, viz., MnCl_2 , MnSO_4 , CoCl_2 , ZnSO_4 , generally retard the reaction rate with the exception of CoCl_2 which accelerates the reaction rate. This accelerating effect is attributed to the electrophilic nature of the salt. Pyridine base has no effect on the reaction. Activation parameters were calculated in each case. Area/volume ratio has no effect on rates and thereby show the non-chain character of the reactions. Main reaction products were identified by preparing derivatives or chromatographically. Mechanisms proposed and rate expressions derived are consistent with the experimental results. Serine oxidation involves a rate determining hydride ion loss with a consequent production of electron deficient transition state which leads to a ready decarboxylation, whereas, methionine and cysteine oxidations involve the steps in which the attacks on sulphur atom are encountered, as sulphur is more nucleophilic than nitrogen.

CHROMIC acid has been employed extensively to oxidise almost all the types of organic substrates namely, carboxylic acids^{1,2}, secondary alcohols³, hydroxy acids⁴, aldehydes and ketones⁵⁻⁸, hydrocarbons⁹ etc. It appears that no work has yet been done on amino acid oxidation by chromic acid from kinetic view point. This prompted us to investigate the kinetics of chromic acid oxidation of some typical amino acids i.e., serine, methionine and cysteine in perchloric acid media.

Experimental

All chemicals were AnalaR grade, used without further purification. All solutions were prepared according to the usual analytical procedures. Redistilled water, used in all kinetic runs, was prepared by successive distillation from dilute alkaline permanganate solution, dil. KHSO_4 and finally, alone.

The reaction vessels were 150 ml stoppered iodine flasks for all kinetic runs. Light was not excluded, as preliminary experiments showed that the results were not significantly different when the experiments were conducted in dark. The reaction vessels were cleaned after every experiment and steamed to get reasonable reproducibility.

The kinetic procedure was as follows: In a thermostat the iodine flasks having the appropriate volume of the standard solutions and redistilled water were kept, chromic acid solution was kept in

a separate flask. Reactions were started by transferring desired volumes of chromic acid in the flask containing amino acid, perchloric acid etc. Ionic strength was kept constant by adding required amounts of sodium perchlorate solution. Aliquot portions (5 ml) were withdrawn at regular intervals and analysed for chromic acid iodometrically. However, in case of cysteine, iodometric estimation fails as cysteine reacts with potassium iodide. As such the progress of the reaction was followed by recording absorbance, at different time intervals, spectrophotometrically at the wavelength 380 μ .

Table 1 shows a typical example of the calculation of rate 'R' and k_o in a single run. Mean values of $[\text{chromic acid}]_{\Delta t}$ and R at the bottom of column 3 and 6 were used in plotting the Figures.

TABLE 1—CALCULATION OF R AND k_o

Time (min)	Titre (ml)	$10^4[\text{Chromic acid}]$ (m)	$10^4\Delta[\text{Chromic acid}]$ (m)	Δt (min)	$10^4 R$ ($\text{mole l}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	$10^4 k_o$ (min^{-1})
0	7.1	10.0	—	—	—	—
30	6.4	9.0	1.0	30	0.33	9.5
60	5.9	8.3	0.7	30	0.23	9.1
90	5.4	7.6	0.7	30	0.23	9.0
120	5.0	7.0	0.6	30	0.20	2.9
150	4.4	6.2	0.8	30	0.26	8.1
180	4.1	5.8	0.4	30	0.13	8.1
	mean	7.7			0.23	8.1

$[\text{Chromic acid}] = 0.001 M$, $[\text{Serine}] = 0.05 M$,
 $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.2 M$, $\mu = 0.5$, Temp. = 30° .

The reaction products were identified in the reaction mixture directly by preparing derivatives and by paper chromatographic technique.

Results

The rate law : Tables 2(A), 3(A) and 4(A) include the rates and rate constants of the reactions of serine (at 50°) methionine and cysteine (at 30°) with chromic acid in perchloric acid media. The concentrations of these organic substrates and perchloric acid are fixed and that of chromic acid

TABLE 2—RATE AND RATE CONSTANT DATA OF SERINE-OXIDATION AT 50° AND $\mu=0.5$, ALL CONCENTRATIONS ARE MOLAR AND R IS IN $\text{mole l}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$ UNITS

A.						
10^4 [Chromic acid]	1.0	2.0	5.0	7.0	10.0	
10^4 [Chromic acid] _{A_v}	0.8	1.6	3.8	5.4	7.5	
10^4 R	0.2	0.4	1.3	1.6	2.9	
10^4k_o	3.1	3.0	3.3	3.1	3.1	
[Serine]=0.05M, [HClO ₄]=0.2M						
B.						
10^4 [Serine]	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
10^4 R	0.9	1.7	2.1	3.2	4.0	4.6
$10^4k_o'$	4.2	9.2	13.9	18.8	24.0	29.9
$10^4k_o'/[\text{Serine}]$	4.2	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.8
[Chromic acid]=0.002M, [HClO ₄]=0.2M						
C.						
10^4 [HClO ₄]	2.0	5.0	10.0	30.0	40.0	
10^4 R	0.8	1.7	3.0	8.1	7.7	
$10^4k_o''$	3.8	9.2	18.9	57.2	77.3	
$10^4k_o''/[\text{HClO}_4]$	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	
[Chromic acid]=0.002M, [Serine]=0.05M.						

TABLE 3—RATE AND RATE CONSTANT DATA OF METHIONINE OXIDATION REACTION AT 30° AND CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH 0.2 (Units as in Table 2)

A.						
10^4 [Chromic acid]	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0	20.0
10^4 [Chromic acid] _{A_v}	0.8	1.3	1.8	2.5	3.2	7.1
10^4 R	2.8	5.4	7.2	9.7	11.5	20.0
10^4k_o	3.7	4.2	4.1	4.1	4.0	4.0
[Methionine]=0.01M, [HClO ₄]=0.05M						
B.						
10^4 [Methionine]	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	
10^4 R	1.0	1.2	1.4	1.8	2.5	
$10^4k_o'$	2.0	4.0	5.8	7.6	9.6	
$k_o'/[\text{Methionine}]$	4.0	4.0	3.9	3.8	3.8	
[Chromic acid]=0.001M, [HClO ₄]=0.05M						
C.						
10^4 [HClO ₄]	1.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
10^4 R	0.3	0.7	1.0	1.1	1.4	1.6
$10^4k_o''$	4.1	9.7	19.4	29.0	38.7	49.6
$10^4k_o''/[\text{HClO}_4]$	4.1	4.8	4.9	4.8	4.8	4.9
[Chromic acid]=0.001M, [Methionine]=0.01M.						

TABLE 4—RATE AND RATE CONSTANT DATA OF CYSTEINE OXIDATION REACTION AT 30° AND $\mu=0.2$ (Units as in Table 2)

A.						
10^4 [Chromic acid]	0.5	0.75	1.0	2.0	4.0	6.0
10^4 [Chromic acid] _{A_v}	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.9	1.7	2.5
10^4 R	1.1	1.8	2.1	4.4	6.1	9.5
10^4k_o	4.8	5.2	4.9	5.3	5.0	5.1
[Cysteine]=0.005M, [HClO ₄]=0.05M						
B.						
10^4 [Cysteine]	2.0	4.0	5.0	8.0	10.0	
10^4 R	1.3	2.1	2.3	2.7	3.3	
$10^4k_o'$	1.7	3.6	4.6	7.7	9.5	
$k_o'/[\text{Cysteine}]$	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.0	
[Chromic acid]=0.001M, [HClO ₄]=0.05M						
C.						
10^4 [HClO ₄]	1.0	2.5	5.0	10.0	12.5	15.0
10^4 R	1.0	1.6	2.3	2.5	3.7	3.9
$10^4k_o''$	1.0	2.4	4.6	9.2	11.5	13.5
$k_o''/[\text{HClO}_4]$	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
[Chromic acid]=0.001M, [Cysteine]=0.005M.						

was varied. Figs. 1A, 2A and 3A show that the plots of rates R against [chromic acid]_{A_v} are linear and satisfy equation(1)

$$R = k_o[\text{Chromic acid}]_{A_v} \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) k_o is the observed rate constant of the reaction. This shows that the order of the reaction in chromic acid is unity in each case.

Figs. 1B, 2B and 3B (data from Tables 2B, 3B and 4B) show that the rates of the reaction are linearly increased by increasing the substrate concentration at constant chromic acid and perchloric acid concentrations and, therefore,

$$R \propto [\text{Substrate}]$$

Similarly, perchloric acid dependence of the reactions is evident from Figs. 1C, 2C and 3C. It is

Fig. 1. Dependence of R on A, [Chromic acid] B, [Serine] and C, [HClO₄] at 50°.

Fig. 2. Dependence of R on A, [Chromic acid] B, [Methionine] and C, [HClO₄] at 30°.

Fig. 3. Dependence of R on A, [Chromic acid] B, [Cysteine] and C, [HClO₄] at 30°.

clear that the rates are directly proportional to perchloric acid concentrations. Moreover, $k_0/[Perchloric\ acid]$ values given in Tables 2C, 3C and 4C are fairly constant for each reaction confirming the aforesaid conclusion. These findings lead to the rate expression.

$$R = k [\text{Chromic acid}][\text{Substrate}][\text{HClO}_4]$$

The plots 1B, 2B and 3B also 1C, 2C and 3C are passing through the origin showing that there is no decomposition of chromic acid in the absence of substrate and perchloric acid.

Table 5 gives the k_0 values obtained from the slopes of Figs. 1A, 2A and 3A. These values are

$10^3 k_0$	Serine	Methionine	Cysteine
	31.0	4.0	5.0

consistent with the mean k_0 values of Tables 2A, 3A and 4A.

The nature of the reactions :

A few experiments were performed in the dark as well. The rate of the reactions is not affected significantly. Similarly area/volume does not alter the rates and suggests non-chain character of the reactions.

Effect of pyridine was studied due to its wide use in chemical reaction as a proton acceptor¹⁰. The dissociation constant of pyridinium ion¹¹ is of the order of 5×10^{-6} at 25°. Pyridine thus effectively removes hydrogen ions and the effective hydrogen ion concentration in the presence of pyridine would correspond to $[H^+] - [Py]$. If pyridine catalyses the oxidation, the value $k_0/([H^+] - [Py])$ is expected to increase in the concentration of pyridine. This value would decrease if pyridine retards the reaction and would be constant if pyridine has no effect on the rate of the oxidation. Reactions were found to be unaffected by pyridine. The results for serine oxidation are listed in Table 6. Similar results were obtained with methionine and cysteine oxidation reactions.

TABLE 6—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR SERINE, METHIONINE AND CYSTEINE OXIDATIONS

	ΔE^\ddagger K cal	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
Serine	16.5	-27.0
Methionine	11.9	-37.1
Cysteine	6.8	-51.1

Salt effect :

Effect of various salts viz., $CoCl_2$, $MnCl_2$, $MnSO_4$ and $ZnSO_4$ on the reactions were examined by adding varying amounts of salt solutions in the reaction mixtures (Table 7A and B). It is evident from the table that no inference can be drawn regarding the effect of ionic strength on reaction rate. However, different ions play important role to influence the reaction rate. Cobalt chloride accelerates the reaction rates slightly while zinc sulphate retards the reaction. The retarding actions of manganese sulphate and manganese chloride are much pronounced, but no MnO_2 is precipitated in presence of Mn^{++} salts. Cobalt chloride is electrophilic in nature, and, therefore, in its presence the solution would be more acidic which causes an increase in the reaction rate. The pronounced decrease in the rates (about 1/3 of that in the absence of Mn^{++}) in presence of Mn^{++} ions is to be expected if Mn^{++} ions catalyse the disproportionation of intermediate valency states of chromium and show that chromium(IV) is involved as an intermediate^{12,13}.

TABLE 7(A)—EFFECT OF SALTS ON THE RATE OF SERINE OXIDATION

Salts Concentration $\times 10^4$ moles/l	Nil	MnCl ₂			MnSO ₄			CoCl ₂			ZnSO ₄		
	—	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0
$k_0 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	3.06	0.18	0.18	0.12	0.18	0.12	0.12	3.14	3.25	3.24	2.88	2.91	2.82

[Chromic acid]=0.01M, [Serine]=0.05M, [Perchloric acid]=0.4M, Temp.=50°.

(B) EFFECT OF SALTS ON THE RATE OF METHIONINE AND CYSTEINE OXIDATION

Salts M $\times 10^3$ mole/l	Nil	MnCl ₂			MnSO ₄			CoCl ₂			ZnSO ₄		
	—	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0
* $k_0 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	9.75	7.46	7.03	7.02	6.16	4.91	4.35	9.99	10.10	10.87	9.13	7.01	6.08
** $k_0 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	4.60	4.35	4.35	4.14	4.39	4.34	4.24	4.54	4.54	4.64	4.93	5.31	5.31

[Chromic acid]=0.001M, $\frac{[\text{Methionine}]}{[\text{Cysteine}]}$ =0.005M, [Perchloric acid]=0.2M, Temp.=30°.

* for methionine oxidation.

** for cysteine oxidation.

Temperature effect :

All the reactions were carried out over the wide temperature ranges e.g., serine oxidation (45-60°), methionine oxidation (20-35°) and cysteine oxidation (25-40°) to evaluate the activation parameters. The results are summarised in Table 8.

TABLE 8—EFFECT OF PYRIDINE ON THE RATE OF SERINE OXIDATION

10 ³ [Pyridine] (m)	10 ³ k ₀ min ⁻¹	10 ³ k ₀ ([H ⁺]-[Py])
0.0	3.06	7.65
1.20	3.07	7.67
2.40	3.04	7.64
3.60	2.94	7.41

[Chromic acid]=0.01M, [Serine]=0.05M, [HClO₄]=0.4M, $\mu=0.5$, Temp.=50°.

The values of energy of activation and entropy of activation for serine resemble with the values required to rupture C-H bond^{1,2}. Low values obtained in the case of methionine and cysteine indicate that attack occurs at sulphur atom³.

Identification of reaction products :

The main reaction products of serine, methionine and cysteine oxidation are glycol aldehyde, methionine sulphoxide and cysteic acid respectively. These were identified as follows :

Glycol aldehyde : 2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazine solution was added to the reaction mixture. Yellow crystals obtained were recrystallised from alcohol and the melting point of phenyl hydrazone derivative was determined. Experimental melting point is concordant with the literature value for glycol aldehyde.

Methionine sulphoxide : Benzoyl chloride and aqueous sodium bicarbonate solutions were added in the reaction mixture. A precipitate of N-benzoyl methionine sulphoxide was obtained which was confirmed by melting point (183°).

Cysteic acid : It was identified chromatographically. The chromatographic sheet was spotted with the reaction product and it was saturated with the vapours of phenol and then it was run in water saturated phenol. Descending chromatography was employed. The temperature was kept between 23-26° during experiment. After the development of chromatogram the sheet was removed from the tank and dried. The paper was then sprayed with 1% solution of ninhydrin in *n*-butanol and heated in an oven for five minutes at 100°. The R_f value comes out to be 0.1 which confirms the presence of cysteic acid, as seen with the authentic sample.

Discussion

Chromic acid oxidation of these amino acids in perchloric acid media is first order with respect to oxidant, reducing substrates and perchloric acid each.

The entropy of activation values for serine and methionine oxidation are consistent with the observed values for α -hydroxy acids⁴.

Westheimer mechanism⁵ applicable to α -hydroxy acids, in which the process is catalysed by bases to decompose the chromate ester formed in the initial step is not applicable in the present case as the reactions are unaffected by pyridine base.

A modification over Westheimer scheme was suggested by Kwart and Francis^{1,4} on which decomposition of chromate ester does not require

the presence of external base as the proton is removed intermolecularly.

Following the views of Kwart and Francis¹⁴ the mechanism for serine oxidation can be given as (1).

In this process rupture of C-C bond occurs which would require an energy of activation over 18 Kcal mole⁻¹ and a small entropy of activation¹⁵, calculated values for present systems make this extremely impossible.

The difficulty is overcome if one proceeds via the mechanism proposed by Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian⁴ for α -hydroxy acids. This mechanism involves a rate determining hydride ion loss with a consequent production of an electron deficient transition state which leads to the ready decarboxylation *in situ* (2).

In the case of methionine oxidation the attack may occur either at nitrogen or at sulphur group⁸.

The product, methionine sulphoxide, forced us to believe that chromic acid attacks the sulphur group. Further, sulphur is more nucleophilic than nitrogen. Accordingly it may transfer electrons easily than amino group. Therefore, it is an electron pair donation by sulphur present in methionine to Cr=O, as in the case of olifine oxidation¹⁶. Mechanism may be shown as (3).

In cysteine oxidation also chromic acid attacks the sulphur present in β -position owing to the reasons stated above. The proposed mechanism is as (4).

Evidently the rate of disappearance of chromic acid for all the three oxidations are given, on the basis of mechanisms, by the rate expression

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{CrO}_3] = k [\text{Chromic acid}] [\text{Substrate}] [\text{H}^+]$$

which is consistent with the experimental results.

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